

Perceptions of Filipino Receiving Teachers on the Adequacy of Professional Preparation for Diverse Learners

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Abstract- This study examined the perceptions of Receiving Teachers regarding the adequacy of their professional preparation for handling diverse learners in inclusive classrooms. Specifically, it assessed seven domains: adequacy of SPED coursework, training in differentiated instruction, assessment literacy, classroom and behavior management, cultural and linguistic responsiveness, practicum exposure and mentorship, and self-assessment of professional competence. Using a descriptive-quantitative design, data were gathered through a Likert-scale survey administered to Receiving Teachers at San Antonio National High School, Zambales. Results showed that Receiving Teachers generally perceived their professional preparation as adequate across all domains, with mean scores ranging from 3.84 to 4.04, all interpreted as "Agree." Self-assessment of professional competence obtained the highest mean ($M = 4.04$), indicating that teachers were confident in their ability to support diverse learners in inclusive settings. Training in differentiated instruction and cultural and linguistic responsiveness both received high ratings ($M = 3.96$), suggesting that teachers felt prepared to address learners' varied needs and backgrounds. In contrast, adequacy of SPED coursework and practicum exposure and mentorship obtained the lowest means ($M = 3.84$), highlighting areas that may benefit from further enhancement. The grand overall mean of 3.92 reflects a generally positive perception of professional preparation. Furthermore, years of teaching experience were not significantly related to perceived adequacy of preparation. The findings may serve as a basis for improving teacher education and professional development programs that support inclusive education.

Keywords- Receiving Teachers, Professional Preparation, Diverse Learners, Inclusive Education, Teacher Readiness, Special Education, Philippine Basic Education.

I. Introduction

Education is a fundamental human right that must be accessible to all learners regardless of their abilities, backgrounds, or circumstances. In the Philippines, the growing presence of diverse learners in general education classrooms has placed increasing demands on teachers who may not have received adequate preparation to address their varied needs. Among these teachers, receiving teachers play a particularly important role as they are the ones who directly accommodate learners with disabilities and other special needs in regular classroom settings.

The implementation of the 2022 Inclusive Education Act remains in its early stages, with many of the promised services and resources still undelivered, making the preparedness of receiving teachers even more critical. [7] Understanding how these teachers perceive their own professional preparation is therefore an important concern that deserves careful scholarly attention. [1]

This study aims to examine Filipino receiving teachers' perceptions of their professional preparation for diverse learners, explore their experiences and competencies in implementing inclusive practices, identify gaps in teacher preparation programs, and propose strategies to strengthen the knowledge, skills, and readiness of SPED teachers in inclusive educational settings.

A. Background of Study

[3] The Philippine government has established strong legal foundations to support inclusive education and the professional readiness of teachers. The 1987 Philippine Constitution establishes the right to education and mandates an integrated education system for all learners, while [4] Republic Act No. 7277 or the Magna Carta for Persons with Disabilities protects the rights of individuals with disabilities to access quality education. Republic Act No. 10533 [5] or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 further defines inclusive education through programs designed to address the physical, intellectual, psychosocial, and cultural needs of all learners including those with disabilities, learners under difficult circumstances, Indigenous Peoples, and the gifted and talented.

Republic Act No. 11650 [6] or the Inclusive Education Act of 2022 mandates that learners with disabilities be given full access to regular schools and calls for the professional development of teachers in inclusive strategies and instructional practices. Despite these laws, the translation of these policies into actual classroom practice remains a work in progress.

Teacher readiness, encompassing knowledge, attitudes, and pedagogical skills, is a critical factor in building inclusive classrooms, yet many teachers feel inadequately trained to implement inclusive strategies effectively. [1] In the Philippine setting, the most commonly reported barrier is the lack of adequate support in handling learners with diverse needs, leaving teachers overwhelmed without proper assistance. Despite growing scholarly attention, a coherent framework for teacher preparation in the Philippine context remains underdeveloped, as existing studies have largely focused on teacher attitudes and general barriers rather than on how receiving teachers themselves evaluate their own professional preparation. [8]

Previous local studies on receiving teacher competencies have focused either on general inclusive education or skill-based assessments disconnected from teachers' actual preparation experiences. This study addresses that gap by centering teacher perceptions, which capture both formal preparation such as university coursework and practicum, and informal learning such as school-based mentoring and workshops. Drawing on differentiated instruction, Universal Design for Learning, and culturally responsive teaching, the study employs a Likert scale instrument to generate

quantifiable indicators of training adequacy in Filipino classrooms serving students with disabilities, indigenous learners, and multilingual learners.

San Antonio National High School in Zambales is one with the advocacy of inclusive education by integrating Special Needs Education (SNED) learners into regular classrooms.

For the school year 2025-2026, the school has a total of 23 SNED learners, with one learner placed in a Grade 7 regular classroom, one in Grade 8, one in Grade 11, and 20 learners under a self-contained program. These learners come from different grade levels and represent the diversity of needs that receiving teachers are expected to accommodate daily. In this context, ten receiving teachers were selected as participants for this study. While the school actively promotes inclusivity to support the holistic development of SNED students, the receiving teachers who interact and work alongside these learners may lack adequate preparation and knowledge about their role in fostering an inclusive environment.

Much of the focus of existing programs has been on curriculum adaptation and teacher training, yet how receiving teachers themselves perceive the adequacy of their professional preparation remains largely unexplored. This study therefore seeks to examine those perceptions, recognizing that understanding the experiences and competencies of receiving teachers is essential in developing meaningful interventions that strengthen inclusive education practice at San Antonio National High School and beyond.

B. Objectives of the Study

This study aims to:

1. To determine Filipino receiving teachers' perceptions of the adequacy of their professional preparation for handling diverse learners.
2. To identify which areas of professional preparation (e.g., adequacy of SPED coursework, training in differentiated instruction, assessment literacy, classroom and behavior management, cultural and linguistic responsiveness, practicum exposure and mentorship, and self-assessment of professional competence.) are perceived as adequate or inadequate by receiving teachers.
3. To analyze the relationship between receiving teachers' demographic or professional variables (training background, years of teaching experience, and school type) and their perceived adequacy of preparation.
4. To formulate recommendations for enhancing teacher education and professional development programs for receiving teachers in the Philippines.

II. Methods

The researchers used a descriptive quantitative research design using a structured Likert scale survey to measure the perceptions of licensed receiving teachers from selected public schools in Zambales. Purposive sampling was used to target in-service teachers with formal responsibilities in inclusive classrooms, such as resource teachers, inclusion teachers, and self-contained class teachers. A formal message was sent directly to the respondents emphasizing the confidentiality of their data and information

as well as the voluntary nature of their participation. The survey was administered online to ensure accessibility and convenience for all respondents.

Variables and Measurement

The data collection instrument is a self-administered questionnaire composed of two sections:

- **Demographic Profile** — covers age, gender, years of experience, highest educational attainment, and Special Needs Education training background.
- **Perceived Adequacy of Professional Preparation** — rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree) across six domains:

- A. Adequacy of Special Needs Education coursework
- B. Training in differentiated instruction
- C. Assessment literacy
- D. Classroom and behavior management
- E. Cultural and linguistic responsiveness
- F. Practicum Exposure and Mentorship
- G. Self- Assessment

Items were adapted and validated based on the frameworks of Tomlinson on differentiation and Universal Design for Learning. [9]

Data Analysis

Frequency and Percentage Distribution were used to describe the demographic and professional profiles of the respondents, including their training background, years of teaching experience, and school type.

Weighted Mean was utilized to determine the perceptions of Filipino Receiving Teachers regarding the adequacy of their professional preparation for handling diverse learners.

Specifically, it was used to assess the respondents' perceptions in the areas of SPED coursework, differentiated instruction, assessment literacy, classroom and behavior management, cultural and linguistic responsiveness, practicum exposure and mentorship, and self-assessed professional competence.

The following scale was used to interpret the weighted mean scores based on the five-point Likert scale employed in the study:

- $4.21 \leq \bar{x} \leq 5.00$ – Strongly Agree
- $3.41 \leq \bar{x} \leq 4.20$ – Agree
- $2.61 \leq \bar{x} \leq 3.40$ – Neutral
- $1.81 \leq \bar{x} \leq 2.60$ – Disagree
- $1.00 \leq \bar{x} \leq 1.80$ – Strongly Disagree

Ranking was used to identify the areas of professional preparation that were perceived as most adequate and least adequate by the respondents.

Standard Deviation was used to determine the variability of the responses and to measure the dispersion of scores from the mean.

A One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine whether significant differences existed in the perceived adequacy of professional preparation when respondents were grouped according to years of teaching experience.

The level of significance for all inferential statistical tests was set at 0.05. The null hypothesis was rejected when the computed p-value was less than 0.05 and accepted when the p-value was greater than or equal to 0.05.

The results of these statistical analyses served as the basis for formulating recommendations aimed at enhancing teacher education and professional development programs for receiving teachers in the Philippines.

III. Results

The Likert scale survey administered to ten receiving teachers at San Antonio National High School in Zambales revealed that respondents generally perceived their professional preparation as adequate for handling diverse learners in inclusive classroom settings, as reflected in a grand overall mean of 3.92 (SD = 0.99). All seven domain means fell within the Agree range of 3.40 to 4.19, consistent with the findings of Raguindin and Ping (2025), who noted that Filipino teachers generally demonstrate a foundational level of readiness for inclusive education, though gaps remain in specific areas of practice. [2]

The table below summarizes the mean scores and standard deviations across all domains:

TABLE I.

DOMAIN	MEAN	SD	INTERPRETATION
Adequacy of SPED Coursework	3.84	0.96	Agree
Training in Differentiated Instruction	3.96	0.97	Agree
Assessment Literacy	3.90	0.89	Agree
Classroom and Behavior Management	3.88	1.02	Agree
Cultural and Linguistic Responsiveness	3.96	0.95	Agree
Practicum Exposure and Mentorship	3.84	1.17	Agree
Self-Assessment	4.04	1.03	Agree
Grand Overall Mean	3.92	0.99	Agree

Fig. 1. SUMMARY OF MEAN SCORES AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS ACROSS ALL DOMAINS

Among the seven domains, Self-Assessment obtained the highest mean of 4.04 (SD = 1.03), indicating that respondents felt most confident in evaluating their own readiness and competencies in inclusive teaching. Training in Differentiated Instruction and Cultural and Linguistic Responsiveness both obtained a mean of 3.96 (SD = 0.97 and 0.95 respectively), reflecting adequate preparation in lesson modification and culturally responsive teaching, consistent with the learner-centered emphasis of Republic Act No. 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. Assessment and Literacy obtained a mean of 3.90 (SD = 0.89), while Classroom and Behavior Management obtained a mean of 3.88 (SD = 1.02), with the latter's higher standard deviation suggesting greater variability in respondents' confidence in managing inclusive classroom dynamics.

Adequacy of SPED Coursework and Practicum Exposure and Mentorship obtained the lowest means of 3.84 (SD = 0.96 and 1.17 respectively), with the notably higher standard deviation in practicum suggesting considerable variation in the quality of hands-on field experiences among respondents. These findings align with RSIS International (2025), which identified inadequate training and support as the most commonly reported barriers in Philippine inclusive education settings, highlighting these two domains as the weakest dimensions of preparation that require priority attention.[8]

Overall, while the findings affirm a general sense of preparedness among receiving teachers, they also underscore the need to strengthen SPED coursework, practicum experiences, and behavior management training in alignment with the mandates of Republic Act No. 11650 or the Inclusive Education Act of 2022, to ensure that all receiving teachers are fully equipped to meet the diverse needs of every learner in their classrooms.[6]

Comparative Analysis: ANOVA on Teaching Experience

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to examine whether perceived adequacy of professional preparation differed significantly across teaching experience groups. Respondents were grouped into three categories with the following group means: Less than 1 Year (M = 3.39), 1 to 6 Years (M = 4.55), and 7 Years and Above (M = 3.58). The analysis yielded an F statistic of 2.95 and a p value of 0.118, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference in perceived adequacy across teaching experience groups. Nevertheless, a notable trend was observed where teachers with 1 to 6 years of experience reported the highest perceived adequacy compared to those with less than 1 year or more than 7 years of experience.

IV. Conclusion and Recommendation

This study concludes that Filipino receiving teachers at San Antonio National High School in Zambales generally perceive their professional preparation as adequate for teaching diverse learners in inclusive classroom settings, as evidenced by a grand overall mean of 3.92 (SD = 0.99) interpreted as Agree. This result is consistent with findings suggesting that Filipino teachers demonstrate a foundational level of readiness for inclusive education, though gaps remain in specific areas of practice. All seven

domains falling within the Agree range indicates that teacher education programs in the Philippines have made meaningful progress in preparing receiving teachers for inclusive classrooms.

The strongest areas of preparation were Self-Assessment (mean of 4.04, SD = 1.03) and Training in Differentiated Instruction and Cultural and Linguistic Responsiveness (both with a mean of 3.96, SD = 0.97 and 0.95 respectively), highlighting the effectiveness of learner-centered and culturally responsive approaches in pre-service teacher education. These findings reflect the growing emphasis on learner-centered approaches under Republic Act No. 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 [5]. Conversely, the relatively lower ratings in Adequacy of SPED Coursework and Practicum Exposure and Mentorship, both with a mean of 3.84 (SD = 0.96 and 1.17 respectively), suggest that these areas must be prioritized in both pre-service curricula and continuing professional development programs.

While no statistically significant differences were found across gender and teaching experience groups, the observed trend favoring early-career teachers with 1 to 6 years of experience points to the possibility that recently trained teachers benefit from more updated and inclusive-focused curricula, while more experienced teachers may have completed their preparation under older frameworks that placed less emphasis on inclusive education principles. Overall, the findings affirm the importance of strengthening the alignment between Philippine teacher education programs and the inclusive education mandates of Republic Act No. 11650 or the Inclusive Education Act of 2022, to ensure that all receiving teachers are fully equipped to meet the diverse needs of every learner in their classrooms [6].

B. Recommendations

Based on the findings, Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) are encouraged to strengthen practicum exposure, mentorship opportunities, and assessment literacy training, as these areas received comparatively lower ratings. At the same time, TEIs should sustain effective preparation in differentiated instruction and self-assessment of professional competence, which were identified as strengths among Receiving Teachers. School administrators should provide continuous professional development and mentoring programs to support teachers in inclusive classroom practice. Since years of teaching experience were not significantly related to perceived preparedness, training opportunities should be accessible to all Receiving Teachers regardless of length of service. The Department of Education should continue supporting the implementation of Republic Act No. 11650 through clear policies and adequate resources for teacher development. Future researchers may employ larger samples and qualitative approaches to gain deeper insights into the preparation and experiences of Receiving Teachers in inclusive education.

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